

Emotional design engineering for packaging of olive oil using Machine Learning techniques

Ana de las Heras^{a}, Francisco Zamora^a, Antonio Ferramosca^b, Amalia Luque^{a,b}*

^aDepartamento de Ingeniería del Diseño. Escuela Politécnica Superior. Universidad de Sevilla. Virgen de África, 7. 41011-Sevilla.Spain.

^bDepartment of Management, Information and Production Engineering, University of Bergamo, Via G. Marconi 5, 24044 Dalmine (BG), Italy

*Corresponding author

emails: adelasheras@us.es; fzpolo@us.es; antonio.ferramosca@unibg.it; amalialuque@us.es;

Abstract

Consumer behaviour, and therefore purchase intentions, are affected by the visual elements of packaging. This is particularly important for products in the agri-food sector, especially for extra virgin olive oil. In this work, the perception of different packaging options by olive oil users is analysed. For this purpose, machine learning tools are used in the synthesis phase of the Kansei Engineering methodology.

On one hand, the four properties of material, colour, price, and capacity were considered for the definition of the property space. These were considered to be the most important properties for the measurement of the user's interaction with the product. On the other hand, for the determination of the semantic space, a literature search was first performed, and then an affinity analysis was carried out, followed by a pilot survey in order to reduce the number of Kanseis. Subsequent to these analyses, the semantic space consisted of 17 and 6 Kanseis, respectively. The final survey was given to a sample of 100 Andalusian (Spanish) citizens. Machine learning

techniques (linear regression, ridge regression, and SVR) were employed for the synthesis phase.

The results show that Kansei Engineering can be used as a tool to optimise the design of olive oil packaging by using machine learning tools in the synthesis phase. This study can provide the basis for other studies of other agri-food products and for the use of other artificial intelligence tools.

Keywords: Kansei Engineering, machine learning, packaging, sustainability, olive oil, SDG

12

Highlights

- Packaging design plays a major role in the overall perception of products.
- Kansei Engineering is used for the study of olive oil packaging.
- A set of 6 representative Kanseis were obtained through PCA and FA.
- The results show a dependence of the Kanseis on the properties of the packaging.
- Machine Learning techniques can be used in the synthesis phase of Kansei Engineering.

Graphical abstract

1. Introduction

Previous studies show that the visual elements of packaging affect consumer behaviour and purchase intentions. Moreover, the material and colours of packaging are very important with respect to the level of attractiveness and, therefore, for consumer preferences [1,2]. In the purchase decision in the case of olive oil, the type of packaging is highly important. This variable increases the consumer's willingness to pay for olive oil [3] and has a significant impact on the price of olive oil [4].

The importance of packaging design in extra virgin olive oil has been previously analysed [5]. In this work, 122 experts were convened to carry out a tasting of extra virgin olive oil. The participants tasted the same product wrapped in different types of packaging. Differences in perception were found. Therefore, the hypothesis of the influence of the perception of the packaging was successfully tested. Consequently, it is important to explore, analyse, and go into greater depth regarding packaging design, in order to ascertain which factors generate a better score in the assessment [6].

Experiential design methodologies put the focus of the design on the user. Therefore, the end user is the protagonist of the design process. For this reason, the variability and richness of the user "group" in the different stages of product design (conceptual design, detail design, materialisation design, manufacturing, direct logistics, use, reverse logistics, and end-of-life) is crucial [7]. However, this diversity is often overlooked. Users are first segmented into interest groups and, subsequently, homogeneous behaviour within these groups is assumed [8].

Kansei Engineering stands out among experiential design methodologies [9,10]. In this methodology, relationships are inferred between the properties of a product with the emotions or feelings (Kanseis) that the product elicits in users [11]. Kansei words are generally adjectives that represent users' emotions and feelings. Generally, evaluations on product design features using Kansei words are necessary for the creation of these relationships.

Therefore, when conducting product design research using Kansei Engineering, it is essential to determine Kansei words are related to the new product and how to elicit Kansei from the consumer when trying to manufacture a new product [12,13]. Traditionally, and for practical reasons in application, Kansei words are adapted to extract users' perception of product design features [12–15]. For this reason, the effective identification of Kansei words to collect users' psychological feelings regarding design features plays a decisive role in this discipline.

Kansei words can be collected from various sources, such as journals, the academic literature, product manuals, product test reports, expert reviews, user opinions, and customer interviews [16,17]. Statistical procedures are often employed to identify relationships between Kansei words and product design features. Furthermore, factor analysis and cluster analysis are commonly used methods for the identification of effective Kansei words in previous Kansei

Engineering studies based on a large amount of questionnaire data [18,19]. This process requires the active participation of collaborators, which is not only costly, but also time-consuming, knowledge-intensive, and labour-intensive [20,21].

Kansei Engineering has been previously applied to ecological design, thereby adopting the name "eco-Kansei" [22]. This methodology has been utilised for the design of chairs [23]. In this regard, differences depending on the packaging material were found in these studies. For example Maleki et al. [22] studied how it affected purchase perception for chocolates. To this end Friedman's test was used, and, among other issues, significant differences were found in Kanseis such as uniqueness, sustainability, modernity, luxury perception, originality, harmlessness, and price perception. Researchers often use the QT1 model to analyse the results from Kansei Engineering studies, in the search for a linear relationship between Kansei valuation and product properties [24].

Although certain studies do propose the use of Kansei Engineering methodology in the field of eco-design, its use is not widespread and remains limited to the design of furniture [25] and clothing [26]. In this respect, more studies should be conducted regarding the impact of packaging on the environment and the need to minimize this impact through design [27,28].

On the other hand, machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence that studies algorithms that improve automatically through experience [29,30]. The applications of machine learning are increasingly numerous [11], and cover issues such as prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of diseases [31], optimisation of economic investments [32], and the implementation of smart cities [29].

Machine learning techniques are also being used in the field of Kansei Engineering. On the one hand, machine learning tools can be utilised in the synthesis phase of the methodology in which the relationship between the opinions expressed by the users (Kanseis) and the properties of the products is sought [11,33]. On the other hand, these algorithms can be used to optimise the proposed design [10,11,34].

Packaging can be evaluated from different points of view: sustainability, manufacturing process, cost, etc. The environmental aspect is a positive point in the purchase decision of users due to the current trend towards the intention to purchase green products, where recyclability, reuse, and recycling are necessary factors [35]. Sustainable packaging design would be related to Sustainable Development Goal 12 (Sustainable Consumption and Production).

There is a growing interest that is increasing the demand for olive oil in the countries of the Mediterranean basin. Among other reasons, proximity, promotion of the local economy, its impact on people's health, promotion of sustainable agriculture, and food sovereignty all deserve mention [36]. In this respect, the design of virgin olive oil packaging is important.

The main contributions of the work are the following:

- The number of studies, that, from the perspective of Kansei Engineering, address the design of virgin olive oil containers remain very limited. Furthermore, this work specifically takes into account the inclusion of Kanseis related to sustainability.
- In general, Kansei Engineering studies are conducted by surveying a small number of respondents and assuming that they are sufficient, without performing any checks related to the number of user surveys. In this paper, we propose verifying that the number of respondents

is sufficient by means of the learning curve, which evaluates the performance of the Machine Learning model as the size of the training set is increased.

- On the other hand, classic Kansei Engineering studies start from a large set of Kanseis, which are selected by ad-hoc techniques (affinity analysis, for example), at the researchers' discretion. Our proposal involves performing a dimensionality reduction of the initial set of Kanseis by means of a first survey on experts and an analysis of the results by means of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Factor Analysis (FA).

Therefore, the objectives of this work include:

General objective:

- To link the properties of olive oil packaging in terms of the emotions and sensations (Kanseis) that packaging provokes in users. In other words, to measure the influence of the attributes on the Kanseis, thereby contributing to the design of better packaging from the point of view of manufacturing needs, policies, and business interests, without harming user perception.

Specific objectives:

- To include environmental factors among the Kanseis and to study specifically how packaging properties influence the environmental perception of packaging.
- To select the Kanseis to be studied by using dimensionality reduction techniques.
- To develop a study where the number of respondents is sufficiently representative for product decision-making.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows. In Section 2, the methodology is presented, both in survey design and data processing. Section 3 describes the main results obtained. Section 4 discusses the results in detail. Section 5 presents the conclusions and future work.

2. Methodology

Figure 1 shows the methodology followed in this work. Two phases can be distinguished. Phase 1 includes the initial search for Kanseis, the elicitation of these through the design and development of a first expert survey, the construction of the property space, and the preparation and delivery of the second survey with the Kanseis reduced to the large group of users. Subsequently, in Phase 2, the processing and treatment of data to obtain the results and their discussion is carried out.

Figure 1. Methodology proposal

2.1. Survey design Phase 1: Preparation and application of the survey

Two surveys have been developed. The first was given to a group of experts. The aim of the first survey was to condense the Kanseis to those that were the most representative, and a second survey was distributed to a large group of users where the relationships that exist between Kanseis and the design of the olive oil packaging are sought via machine learning techniques for the treatment of this data.

2.1.1. Space of product properties

The most important virgin olive oil packaging characteristics must be selected. In this case, there are 4 decision areas that make up the attributes of olive oil packaging: material, colour, price, and capacity. These four categories have been selected as those of greatest importance for the measurement of user interaction with the product [37].

For olive oil, packaging plays a key role in the preservation of its properties, since the quality of olive oil deteriorates, especially with exposure to high temperatures, air, and light. Thus, the search for containers that maintain the physicochemical and organoleptic properties of the oil for a longer period is a major determining factor. From an eminently technical point of view, there is an abundance of work on the packaging of olive oils. Several studies have concluded that glass bottles, especially opaque bottles, preserve olive oils better than do PVC containers, since they provide greater protection against oxidation [38–41]. Other authors conclude that the best packaging system for extra virgin olive oil is the can, followed by glass bottles [42]. Finally, in a study in which different types of materials were tested, it was concluded that the PET bottle and the can are the most appropriate for packaging extra virgin olive oil because they better preserve its sensory and nutritional attributes [43]. Based on these studies, the materials chosen were glass, plastic, and metal. Likewise, these are the most commonly used materials on the market.

Regarding the labels of olive oils that are marketed in the European Union, the EU Delegated Regulation 2018/1096 of the Commission of May 22 [44], referring to the marketing of olive oil, regulates the elements and characteristics with which the labels of each type of oil must comply, and amends the Implementing Regulation (EU) No 29/2012 with regard to the requirements applicable to certain indications on the labels of olive oil. In said regulation, the mandatory elements that labels must bear include sales denomination of the product, the list and quantity of ingredients, expiration date, special conditions in conservation and in its use, and the place of origin, among others. However, the colours of the labels are not addressed. From a survey with experts, the colours most frequently used on olive oil labels are yellow and green for backgrounds (in different shades and in various figures and drawings) together with black and white for lettering. Figure 2 shows the coding of the colours chosen based on a survey of 20 labels and containers of different brands marketed in Spain.

Figure 2. (a) The background colour of a label, and (b) font colour of a label

With regard to bottle size, subsequent to conducting a market study, it was determined that the most common capacities are 1 litre and 5 litres; these two volumes are considered in the study.

Finally, with respect to price, an investigation was carried out regarding the main distributors selling oil to the final consumer in Andalusia (Spain) in the year 2022, and price ranges have

been established based on calculations of averages and maximum and minimum prices for each type of the following configurations of material and capacity. Table 1 shows the various possible configurations according to material, container capacity, and price.

Table 1. Packaging configurations and price ranges

Material	Bottle capacity	Price 1 (cheap)	Price 2 (expensive)
Glass	1 litre	5 euros	7 euros
Glass	5 litres	35 euros	45 euros
Plastic	1 litre	4 euros	6 euros
Plastic	5 litres	19 euros	24 euros
Metal	1 litre	7 euros	10 euros
Metal	5 litres	27 euros	33 euros

Therefore, the property space consists of 24 products: a combination of 3 materials, with 2 capacities, 2 label colours, and 2 price levels each.

2.1.2. Semantic space and dimensionality reduction

For the development of the questionnaire, a selection is required of what Nagamachi, creator of the Kansei methodology, called "Kanseis evaluations", hereinafter labelled Kanseis. These entities include verbs, nouns, adjectives, and even phrases [45]. The set of Kanseis to be studied is called the semantic space.

For the elicitation of the initial Kanseis, the group of researchers of the study carried out a search for similar terms in books, articles, journal advertisements, web pages, etc. [46–50]. A total of 50 Kanseis were obtained in this first search phase. However, in Kansei Engineering

studies, a reduced semantic space is often employed [48]. The first selection of adjectives is frequently excessively broad, and the completion of the survey would require a considerable amount of time on the part of the respondents. This aspect would make the experiment unaffordable, and hence the set of adjectives is usually reduced to a smaller number. To obtain the reduced semantic space, a qualitative reduction, a quantitative reduction, or a combination of the two types of reductions can be chosen [48].

Table 2 shows a review of the literature. The number of Kanseis used in each phase and the number of respondents are reflected in this table.

Table 2. Semantic space reduction process based on previous work in the literature

Reference	Number of Kanseis	Number of people interviewed
Marco Almagro (2011) [48]	Initial 123. Final: 13 (affinity analysis)	Reduction: 6. Final survey: 24
Kang (2021) [47]	Initial: 12. Final: 4 (Factor Analysis)	Final survey: 300
Ding et al. (2021) [46]	Initial: 10. Final: 1	Reduction: 30. Final survey: 50
Gan et al (2021) [51]	Final: 10	Reduction: 50. Final survey: 484
Chen et al. (2021) [52]	Initial: 20. Final: 5 (lexical similarity)	Final survey: 30
Cok et al. (2022) [53]	Final: 15	Final survey: 59
Ding, Zhao, et al. (2021) [54]	Initial: 10. Final: 1	Final survey: 50

In the development of questionnaires, there are several strategies [48]:

- The use of the Likert scale.
- The use of the semantic differential.
- The use of visual scales.

Visual analogic scales are not commonly used, in which respondents point along a continuum between two extremes. The Likert scale, named after Rensis Likert, seeks to identify the degree of agreement with a statement [55]. In the semantic differential, first proposed by Charles E. Osgood, the user must choose between a pair of antonymous adjectives [56]. There are two common problems both in the case of Likert scales and in the case of the semantic differential [48]: the first consists of centrality bias, whereby most users tend to score in central values; on the other hand, there is a certain inclination towards agreement that tends to positively value the adjective that is considered as positive. It has previously been shown that semantic differential surveys are better than Likert scales in the face of acquiescence bias [48,57]. One of the limitations found in the semantic differential is that there is not always an antonym. In these cases, the choice between an adjective and its constructed opposite as "non-adjective" is often used [58]. In the field of Kansei Engineering, the 5-point and 7-point scales are the most commonly used [48].

In the research carried out herein, 50 initial Kanseis were first selected, and, through an affinity analysis performed by the researchers of the work, the number of Kanseis was then reduced to 17. The 17 selected Kanseis are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Kansei selection following the affinity analysis carried out by the researchers

Kansei ID	Kansei
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K1	Traditional	Modern
K2	Expensive	Cheap
K3	Useless	Useful
K4	Daily	Exceptional
K5	Ugly	Attractive
K6	Unhealthy	Healthy
K7	Unpleasant	Delicious
K8	Unrecognisable	Recognisable
K9	Colourless	Coloured
K10	Non-recyclable	Recyclable
K11	Non-reusable	Reusable
K12	Non-recycled	Recycled
K13	Unsustainable	Sustainable
K14	Non-quality	Quality
K15	Ordinary	Unique
K16	Artificial	Natural
K17	Anodyne	Interesting

A dimensionality reduction by means of quantitative procedures was subsequently carried out. To this end, a first survey was given to a group of 12 design experts with a minimum experience of 4 years of professional experience. In this survey, the respondents evaluated a set of 24 samples of olive oil containers and rated the 17 Kanseis shown in Table 3.

For the presentation of the Kanseis, the semantic differential was used and a 5-point scale was chosen. In this expert survey, in addition to the rating of the various packages, a free-text

question was incorporated to indicate possible improvements in the presentation of the survey for successive versions. The survey was delivered using the Google Forms software tool in a manner similar to previous studies [59,60]. Numerous papers justify the use of telematic surveys versus paper surveys [60,61]. The products were displayed in a randomised fashion. Figure 3 presents the images of the 24 product combinations as shown to the respondents. In this figure, the attributes: container material (glass, plastic, and metal), label colour (green and yellow), price (cheap and expensive), and capacity (1 litre and 5 litres) are shown.

Figure 3. Product images (24 combinations)

For Kanseis reduction, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with and without rotation and Factor Analysis (FA) with and without rotation using the Python programming language [62]

were applied. The packages scikit-learn [63] and FactorAnalyzer [64] were also used. As previously recommended, the results obtained were standardised for each of the Kanseis [65].

The FA and PCA techniques are closely related since they both examine the interdependence between variables [48]. Several authors consider the latter as a stage of the former while others consider them to be totally different techniques. Principal Component Analysis strives to find components (factors) that successively explain most of the total variance, while FA seeks factors that explain most of the common variance [66]. Factor Analysis distinguishes between common variance and unique variance. The common variance is the part of the variance of the variable that is shared with the other variables. The unique variance is the part of the variance of the variable that is specific to that variable. In contrast, PCA makes no such distinction between the two types of variances; it focuses solely on the total variance. While PCA seeks linear combinations of the original variables that explain most of the total variance, FA seeks a new set of variables, smaller in number than the set of original variables, that expresses what is common to those variables; this methodology also helps to confirm whether a priori factors are the most appropriate.

Factor Analysis assumes that there is a common factor underlying all the variables, while PCA creates a hypothesis, whereby the first factor or component would be that which explains most of the total variance, the second factor would be that which explains most of the remaining variance (i.e., that which was not explained by the first factor), and so on. In order to select the appropriate model, researchers must consider what objectives they are looking for in their research, whilst bearing in mind that these methods are based on differences in variances.

Hair et al. (1999) [66] point out that the complications of FA have led to a more widespread use of PCA, although they do mention that empirical research has shown similar results in many cases. Their work shows that the same results can be achieved if the number of variables exceeds 30 or the shared variances exceed 0.6 for most of the variables. These two techniques will therefore be applied in the study and their results will be compared in order to draw conclusions regarding the reduction of the number of Kanseis.

2.1.3. Application of the survey to the large group

The last step of the first phase is to conduct a user survey in order to obtain the data that is to be processed in the second phase and from which the conclusions of the study can be drawn. Once the survey has been designed with the 24 product combinations and with the 6 Kanseis to be evaluated by semantic difference, it is launched for the target population. The first problem is to fix the sample size. To this end, the following formula is used [67]:

$\text{Sample size} = \frac{\frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2}}{1 + \left(\frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2 N}\right)}$	(1)
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where N is the population size, e is the margin of error (percentage expressed as decimal places), and z is a standardised value. The z-score is the number of standard deviations that a given proportion deviates from the mean. The z-score is standardised and can be obtained from tables.

In this study, the profile of users who purchase olive oil were taken as the population of Andalusia (Spain), between 18 and 65 years of age. According to INE [68], this user profile in 2022 contained 5,532,774 people.

A confidence level of 95% was assumed ($z=1.96$) and an error of 10%. Given these assumptions, the required sample size was calculated to be 97 respondents. The survey was administered using the Google Forms software tool, following the same criteria established in the previous section. The containers were shown randomly and the Kanseis were shown on all occasions in the same order as that in Table 7. A total of 100 respondents were obtained, in excess of the minimum number required for the expected level of confidence and error. The distributed questionnaire conformed to the ethical principles of the Helsinki declaration. Each participant received a brief introduction and signed an informed consent [10].

The survey included demographic data, such as age, gender, marital status, level of education, employment status, monthly household income, type of household, number of household members under 16 years of age, province of residence, number of monthly olive oil purchases, places of purchase, and annual consumption of extra virgin olive oil.

2.2. Data processing and treatment (Phase 2)

In this phase, the relationship between the Kansei and the properties of the olive oil containers is to be analysed using Machine Learning techniques. The result of the adjustment corresponds to the Kansei to be predicted, and the 5 entries refer to the dummy properties of the product (see Table 4). For each individual response (each product rated by each respondent), 24 ratings (products) are obtained. Thus, the total number of samples amounts to 2400 (24 products and 100 respondents). These samples are divided into a training set, a validation set, and a test set, in a proportion of 60%, 20%, and 20%, respectively.

Table 4. Dummy variables of the study

X0	X1	Material	X2	Label	X2	Price	X4	Capacity
0	0	Glass	0	Green	0	Cheap	0	1 litre
1	0	Metal	1	Yellow	1	Expensive	1	5 litres
0	1	Plastic						

Among the Machine Learning techniques used for identification, both linear and non-linear models can be used. Various approaches can be employed to fit a non-linear model. The linear problem could be transformed into a non-linear model by adding columns of squares and double products, and of cubes, etc. for powers of higher order. This approach can be confusing and results in a matrix of many columns. As an alternative to this option, a non-linear model can be used. In this paper, two non-linear models have been used: the KernelRidge and the SVR models. Both use the "kernel trick" that renders the resulting model non-linear. Specifically, a Gaussian kernel ("RBF" in sklearn terminology) has been utilised.

When the "kernel trick" is used, the dual problem is solved, but not the primal problem. In the primal problem there is a design (training) matrix of 2,400 rows (samples) and 5 columns (attributes) and the 6 coefficients w are calculated, one per attribute plus the independent term. In contrast, in the dual problem, the alpha coefficients (2,400) are calculated, one per sample.

In the case of using an "RBF" (Gaussian) kernel, the equivalent of the 2,400 dual coefficients are an infinite number of primal coefficients. In the case of the polynomial ("poly") kernel, the number of primal coefficients is large but finite.

The other option is to fit a linear model. In this work, edge regression (Ridge with linear Kernel) has been used. This methodology enables the obtained coefficients to be interpreted later, and

becomes a question of "explainability". The lambda coefficient is introduced in the model "by hand" by observing on the graph which lambda coefficient makes the minimum cost J. The learning curve is calculated to show that the number of samples used in the training is sufficient.

3. Results

3.1. Final selection of the number of Kanseis

For the reduction of the number of Kanseis, an affinity analysis was carried out by the group of researchers [69]. As a result of this step, a reduced number of 17 Kanseis was obtained as represented in Table 3.

However, the number of Kanseis remained very high [48]. For this reason, a clustering by quantitative methods was carried out. For this purpose, PCA with and without rotation and FA with and without rotation was carried out. The analysis was performed with the obtained normalised scores. For each of these systems, weighting coefficients were obtained for each of the variables (e.g., Table 4 for PCA without rotation). For each of the components, the name of the Kansei with the highest weighting in each principal component was assigned to each component (Table 5).

Table 5. Coefficients associated with each of the factors (maximum per Kansei in **bold**, maximum per coefficient underlined)

Kansei	Coeff. F1	Coeff. F2	Coeff. F3	Coeff. F4	Coeff. F5
K1	<u>-0.3093</u>	0.1378	-0.2239	0.0472	0.0303
K2	-0.2638	-0.3883	-0.0356	-0.0661	-0.1440

K3	-0.2605	-0.3824	-0.0264	-0.0924	-0.1810
K4	-0.2153	0.1919	-0.1153	0.1253	<u>-0.5542</u>
K5	-0.2751	0.2824	-0.1595	-0.0837	0.0304
K6	-0.2879	-0.1304	-0.1286	-0.0029	0.3324
K7	-0.0408	-0.0695	-0.1639	<u>0.8400</u>	0.0900
K8	-0.2624	0.2009	0.2270	0.0680	0.1617
K9	-0.2969	-0.1487	-0.0438	0.0148	0.4067
K10	-0.1873	<u>-0.4096</u>	0.1473	-0.0663	-0.2772
K11	-0.2091	0.2691	0.2839	-0.0222	-0.3969
K12	-0.1203	-0.0931	<u>0.5491</u>	0.3629	-0.0139
K13	-0.3038	0.2286	-0.1235	0.0107	0.1031
K14	-0.2390	0.2737	0.0928	-0.2660	0.1382
K15	-0.2168	0.1449	0.4490	0.0674	0.0948
K16	-0.2982	-0.2699	-0.0570	-0.1264	0.0398
K17	-0.1571	0.1149	-0.4241	0.1538	-0.2291

In addition to the 4 analyses performed with Python, calculations with SPSS software and its FactorAnalyzer tool with and without rotation were also carried out, which is equivalent to performing the two methods described above with Python. These calculations were carried out to reinforce the results and to ascertain whether there were any flaws in the results. The calculations were therefore performed yielding 6 results (PCA, FA, and FactorAnalyzer, each with and without rotation). Derived from the analysis of all the coefficients (example Table 5), the following selected Kanseis were obtained for each of the proposed methods (Table 6).

Table 6. Representative Kanseis for each of the factors according to the criteria analysed

PCA without rotation	PCA with rotation	Factor Analysis without rotation	Factor Analysis with rotation	FactorAnalyzer without rotation	FactorAnalyzer with rotation
Traditional - Modern (K1)	Unsustainable - Sustainable (K13)	Artificial - Natural (K16)	Useless - Useful (K3)	Unsustainable - Sustainable (K13)	Unsustainable - Sustainable (K13)
Non-recyclable - Recyclable (K10)	Non-recyclable - Recyclable (K10)	Non-quality - Quality (K14)	Ugly - Attractive (K5)	Non-recyclable - Recyclable (K10)	Expensive - Cheap (K2)
Non-recycled - recycled (K12)	Non-recycled - Recycled (K12)	Non-recycled - Recycled (K12)	Non-recycled - Recycled (K12)	Non-recycled - Recycled (K12)	Non-recycled - Recycled (K12)
Unpleasant - Delicious (K7)	Unpleasant - Delicious (K7)	Unpleasant - Delicious (K7)	Non-quality - Quality (K14)	Unpleasant - Delicious (K7)	Colourless - Coloured (K9)
Daily - Exceptional (K4)	Daily - Exceptional (K4)				Unpleasant - Delicious (K7)

The most frequently occurring Kanseis can be extracted from the table above. Table 7 shows the frequency of occurrence of the Kanseis in the study.

Table 7. Representative Kanseis for each of the factors according to the criteria analysed

Kansei	Frequency
Non-recycled - Recycled (<i>K12</i>)	6
Unpleasant - Delicious (<i>K7</i>)	5
Non-recyclable - Recyclable (<i>K10</i>)	3
Unsustainable - Sustainable (<i>K13</i>)	3
Daily - Exceptional (<i>K4</i>)	2
Non-quality - Quality (<i>K14</i>)	2
Traditional - Modern (<i>K1</i>)	1
Artificial - Natural(<i>K16</i>)	1
Useless - Useful (<i>K3</i>)	1
Ugly - Attractive (<i>K5</i>)	1
Expensive - Cheap (<i>K2</i>)	1
Colourless - Coloured (<i>K9</i>)	1

For the development of the survey to be implemented on the large group of respondents, the first 6 Kanseis in terms of frequency of occurrence were chosen (see Table 8). This number of Kanseis would lie within the most used intervals since, according to the literature review carried out by Marco Almagro (2011) [48], the average number of Kansei adjectives used in the studies was 12. In this same work, a literature review of the number of stimuli that were presented was carried out and 75% of the studies used fewer than 36 stimuli [48]. The final surveys were carried out with the 6 Kanseis with the highest frequency and the 24 products resulting from the possible options with the described variables. These products were randomly coded in order not to act as a limitation in the study.

Table 8. Selection of Kanseis for the user survey

Selected Kanseis
K1: Unpleasant - Delicious
K2: Non-recyclable - Recyclable
K3: Daily - Exceptional
K4: Non-recycled - Recycled
K5: Non-quality - Quality
K6: Unsustainable - Sustainable

3.2. Calculations and results of the user survey

Responses from 100 respondents were obtained. Packaging properties were coded as set out in Table 4. We follow a model similar to that proposed in [48].

From Table 4 it can be inferred that there are 9 dummy variables. However, there are linear relationships between the different variables: Variable x_{22} is linearly dependent on x_{21} ; variable x_{32} is linearly dependent on x_{31} ; variable x_{42} is linearly dependent on x_{41} ; and variable x_{13} is linearly dependent on the remaining two variables.

For that reason, only x_{11} , x_{12} , x_{21} , x_{31} , and x_{41} are considered in the linear regression. This is equivalent to assuming that the coefficients β_{13} , β_{22} , β_{32} , and β_{42} are equal to 0.

$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_{11}x_{11} + \beta_{12}x_{12} + \beta_{13}x_{13} + \beta_{21}x_{21} + \beta_{22}x_{22} + \beta_{31}x_{31} + \beta_{32}x_{32} + \beta_{41}x_{41} + \beta_{42}x_{42} + \epsilon$	(2)
---	-----

In the category score, a score for each of the properties is proposed, and hence a new regression model is proposed where the coefficients are non-zero.

For this purpose, a new linear regression is proposed:

$Y = \beta'_0 + \beta'_{11}x_{11} + \beta'_{12}x_{12} + \beta'_{13}x_{13} + \beta'_{21}x_{21} + \beta'_{22}x_{22} + \beta'_{31}x_{31} + \beta'_{32}x_{32} + \beta'_{41}x_{41} + \beta'_{42}x_{42} + \epsilon$	(3)
---	-----

The relationship between the coefficients of Equations 4 and 5 are as follows:

$\beta'_{jk} = \beta_{jk} + Q_j$	(4)
----------------------------------	-----

$\sum_{k=1}^{c_j} P_k (\beta_{jk} + Q_j) = 0$	(5)
---	-----

where P_k is the probability of occurrence of the k class.

For example, for the second class:

$P_1 \cdot (\beta_{21} + Q_1) + P_2 \cdot (\beta_{22} + Q_1) = 0$	(6)
---	-----

Therefore,

$Q_1 = \frac{-(P_1\beta_{21} + P_2\beta_{22})}{P_1 + P_2} = -(P_1\beta_{21} + P_2\beta_{22})$	(7)
---	-----

In this case, $\beta_{22} = 0$. Hence,

$Q_1 = -(P_1\beta_{11})$	(8)
--------------------------	-----

$\beta'_{11} + \beta'_{12} = \beta_{11} - P_1\beta_{11} - P_1\beta_{11}$	(9)
--	-----

In this case, P_1 is equal to 0.5, and the sum of the coefficients is equal to 0:

For the first group of variables:

$P_1 \cdot (\beta_{11} + Q_3) + P_2 \cdot (\beta_{12} + Q_3) + P_3 \cdot (\beta_{13} + Q_3) = 0$	(10)
--	------

Therefore,

$Q_3 = \frac{-(P_1\beta_{11} + P_2\beta_{12} + P_3\beta_{13})}{P_1 + P_2 + P_3} = -(P_1\beta_{11} + P_2\beta_{12} + P_3\beta_{13})$	(11)
---	------

In this case, $\beta_{13} = 0$, and for this reason:

$Q_3 = -(P_1\beta_{11} + P_2\beta_{12})$	(12)
--	------

Again, in this case, the sum of the new coefficients β' is equal to 0. This is due to the probability of occurrence of each of the classes being the same. This would not be the case if they differed from each other.

The equations for calculating the corrected coefficients:

$0.5 * \beta_{21} + Q_2 = 0 \rightarrow Q_2 = -0.5 * \beta_{21}$	(13)
--	------

$\beta'_{21} = \beta_{21} + Q_2 = \beta_{21} - 0.5 * \beta_{21} = 0.5 * \beta_{21}$	(14)
---	------

Similarly, Equations 15 and 16 can be derived:

$\beta'_{31} = 0.5 * \beta_{31}$	(15)
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$\beta'_{41} = 0.5 * \beta_{41}$	(16)
----------------------------------	------

For the first of the properties, which has three levels, it holds that

$0.33 * \beta_{11} + 0.33 * \beta_{12} + Q_1 = 0 \rightarrow Q_1 = -0.33 * \beta_{11} - 0.33 * \beta_{12}$	(17)
--	------

$\beta'_{11} = \beta_{11} - 0.33 * \beta_{11} - 0.33 * \beta_{12} = 0.66 * \beta_{11} - 0.33 * \beta_{12}$	(18)
--	------

$\beta'_{12} = \beta_{12} - 0.33 * \beta_{11} - 0.33 * \beta_{12} = 0.66 * \beta_{12} - 0.33 * \beta_{11}$	(19)
--	------

For the first of the Kanseis, the coefficients obtained for each of the 5 dummies are:

Table 9. Coefficients of the linear regression

β_{11}	β_{12}	β_{21}	β_{31}	β_{41}
-0.2865	-0.2030	-0.1210	0.03524	0.03171

Using Equations 14-19, it is possible to obtain the corrected coefficients or category scores (see Table 10).

Table 10. Category scores

β'_{11}	β'_{12}	β'_{21}	β'_{31}	β'_{41}
-0.12346	-0.03956	-0.06049	0.017618	0.015853

The remaining coefficients can be obtained by considering that the sum of the category scores in this case is 1 (Table 11).

Table 11. Remaining category scores

β'_{31}	β'_{22}	β'_{32}	β'_{42}
0.16302	0.06049	-0.0176	-0.0158

These results, obtained analogously for the remaining Kanseis, are summarised in Table 11.

Figure 4 shows the mean value of the Kansei when $x_0=0$ and $x_0=1$.

Figure 4. Graph of the mean value K1

As can be observed, the mean (Figure 4) Kansei value is slightly and negatively influenced by the value of attribute x_0 . The median (orange line) is higher for $x_0 = 0$ than for $x_0 = 1$. Again, there is a slight negative dependence between K_1 and attribute x_0 .

The fit of the linear part can now be analysed. It should be borne in mind that, when x has only 2 values, it is meaningless to say whether the relationship is linear or non-linear. For two points, only a straight line is indicated. For each Kansei, the linear part fits a regression line, with edge regression. The coefficients of this line are obtained, with which conclusions can be drawn as to the intensity and direction of the relationship between each attribute and the Kansei.

Thus, for example, x_0 has the greatest (negative) influence on K_1 , with a value of -0.286.

Attributes x_1 and x_2 also (negatively) influence K_1 , but with smaller coefficients than x_0 .

Attributes x_3 and x_4 exert very little influence on K_1 .

Figure 5 shows the cost-lambda curve for K_1 to find the optimal lambda. Two optimisers were used in order to compare the data. This figure shows the results for the "Ridge" optimiser. This optimiser uses edge regression, that is, linear regression with Tikhonov regularisation [70]. It is observed that the optimal lambda is approximately 240. In contrast, if the Support Vector Regression (SVR) model [71] is used, then the optimal lambda is approximately 0.01 as shown in the resulting curve in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Cost-lambda curve for the Ridge optimiser for K1

Considering both graphs, the optimal cost with SVR is not lower than that with the Ridge optimiser. However, SVR is more complicated, slower, and more difficult to interpret in terms of the influence of an attribute on a Kansei. Therefore, the Ridge optimiser has been used in all Kanseis since it allows the result of the obtained coefficients to be physically interpreted (explainability).

Finally, the check was performed that confirmed that the amount of data is sufficient for the results to be consistent for the Ridge model (Figure 6). In this figure of the training data for the Kansei K_1 , the cost function reaches an approximately stable value (with oscillations, but they still tend to be stable) from 150-200 samples. Therefore, for this model, there is sufficient data.

Figure 6. Plot of the number of samples for the Ridge model for K1

This analysis, exemplified for K1, has been repeated for all 6 Kanseis, for each of which similar plots were obtained.

The results of the analyses of all the Kanseis were then compiled so that conclusions could be drawn.

In Figure 7, for each Kansei, the beta coefficients of the regression line (with their signs) can be observed. The K3 Kansei (Daily/Exceptional) is negatively affected by the plastic attribute, since this material is associated to the everyday sphere; for that Kansei, high price values are associated with exceptional use. For K5, plastic and, to a lesser extent, metal containers, negatively affect the perception of product quality. Regarding recyclability (K2),

all coefficients remain close to 0 in all attributes.

Figure 7. Beta coefficients for all Kanseis

Figure 8 shows the absolute values of beta. The plastic material is strongly related to the quality and exceptionality of the product. As mentioned earlier, this attribute influences all Kanseis (negatively in all cases). On the other hand, the metallic packaging of the product also influences all the Kanseis, in that this type of packaging does not offer quality to the user, and is an unpleasant and not very recyclable product.

As for colour, capacity, and price, their influences are less prominent, and hence it is necessary to break down the combined data into other results in order to complement them.

Figure 8. Graph of beta coefficients for all Kanseis as absolute values

Figure 9 represents the average value of beta coefficients for all Kanseis. The importance of each of the properties can therefore be analysed using these average values. As can be observed, the material attributes (plastic and metal) exert a greater influence on users' decision-making. Likewise, colour, as the next most influential attribute, , appeals to the aesthetic factors of the product.

Figure 9. Mean values of all the Kanseis grouped together

Figure 10 shows the results for the Ridge model for K1-K6.

Figure 10. Average values of the model adjusted by the Ridge model for K1-K6

4. Discussion

The results presented in the previous section are discussed below.

Regarding the expert survey and the application in Python of the two methods, PCA and FA, it can be observed in Table 6 (Kanseis associated with each method) that the number of factors to be incorporated into the study depends on the type of factorisation carried out. Traditionally, PCA and FA via the SPSS computer tool are used indistinctly. In this research, we have chosen to analyse the survey results for Kansei clustering by means of four methods using Python for data analysis, as well as the complementary calculation of data analysis using SPSS. These results have provided information to the study, endorsing the ordering by frequency of each of the Kanseis and improving decision-making by those most representative.

We have chosen to use normalised data because, in the case of Python programming, the factorisation results with normalisation differ from those without normalisation.

Regarding the number of respondents, according to the study conducted by Marco Almagro (2011) [48], the number of respondents in Kansei Engineering studies ranges from 9 to 159 participants, the average being found to be 40 participants. Only 10% of the studies analysed

use more than 80 respondents. In the case study, 100 surveys have been employed, of which, together with the results of the application of the sample size, 97 had to be collected for a confidence level of 95% and an error of 10%. On the other hand, based on graphs of the results of the training curves (Figure 6), it is observed that the curves are oscillating, albeit smoothly, and remain constant from the 150 samples. In this case, there are 2,400 samples, the result of the 24 products evaluated by each of the 100 respondents. It can be concluded that the number of surveys collected is sufficiently representative for the sample.

The main objective of this work is to measure the influence of the attributes on the Kanseis. For this purpose, the results shown in Table 11 are used, where the coefficients obtained for the Ridge method are shown.

Table 12. Corrected coefficients for all dummies

	C11 Metal	C12 Plástic	C13 Glass	C21 Yellow	C22 Green	C31 Expensive	C32 Cheap	C41 5 litres	C42 1 litre
K1: Unpleasant - Delicious	-0.1234	-0.0396	0.16302	-0.0604	0.0605	0.0176	-0.0176	0.0176	-0.0159
K2: Non-recyclable - Recyclable	-0.0924	-0.0956	0.1881	-0.0080	0.0080	-0.0072	0.0072	0.0275	-0.0275
K3: Daily - Exceptional	0.2557	-0.3910	0.1352	-0.0495	0.0495	0.0503	-0.0503	0.0515	-0.0515

K4: Non-recycled - Recycled	- 0.0091	-0.0974	0.1065	- 0.0212	0.0213	0.0119	-0.0119	-0.0003	0.0004
K5: Non-quality - Quality	- 0.0686	-0.1392	0.2077	- 0.0445	0.0445	0.0344	-0.0344	-0.0344	- 0.0262
K6: Unsustainable - Sustainable	- 0.0284	-0.1532	0.1817	- 0.0201	0.0201	-0.0068	0.0068	0.0126	- 0.0126

From the results presented in Table 11, it can be inferred that users value both glass containers and green labels positively (all coefficients are positive).

As for price, the results are inconclusive, and therefore the final choice depends on which Kansei is to be given priority in the design. Finally, regarding the variable referring to capacity, according to the study the 5-litre capacity would be the most appropriate (it has positive ratings for the majority of the Kanseis).

In light of these results, the packaging shown in Figure 11 could be recommended since it possesses the material, colour, and capacity properties that have been found to elicit the desired emotions in users.

Figure 11. Emotional design of packaged olive oil using Machine Learning techniques

5. Conclusions

In this work, a selection of the main Kanseis concerning olive oil packaging has been made. For this purpose, a first selection was made by the researchers, followed by a study of the results of a pilot survey analysed by means of PCA and FA. In this way, a series of Kanseis were proposed that can be used for the packaging of other agri-food products such as bottles of wine and cans of soft drinks.

Furthermore, the study includes environmental factors within the Kanseis (Kanseis 2, 4, and 6), and maintains the current trend of incorporating the environmental footprint into purchasing decisions and product purchase preference, thereby influencing users [35,72,73].

The results show trends that enable the type of packaging to be chosen in order to create certain valuations in consumers.

On the other hand, the results can be useful for policy-makers to the extent that they can inform/train citizens to change their preferences towards choices of a more sustainable nature.

This work forms part of a broader line of research in terms of sustainable packaging design. The limitations of this study therefore constitute possibilities for future work, given that the research group will continue working on this line of research.

Among these potential lines of future work are those of the segmentation of the results in terms of user profiles, the use of ANOVA to determine the influence between attributes and Kanseis, and an extension of the correlation analysis.

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